

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Enhanced production of aromatic hydrocarbons and phenols by catalytic co-pyrolysis of **fruit** and garden pruning wastes

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FIGURES

Fig. S1. Schematic representation of the lab-scale fixed bed reactor.

Description:

The lab-scale set up used for the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis experiments in this work is a downdraft fixed bed stainless-steel reactor (16 mm i.d and 400 mm length) equipped with two heating zones, pyrolysis and catalytic. The reaction temperatures are monitored by two type K thermocouples, located on the pyrolysis zone (char bed) and on the catalytic zone (catalyst bed), respectively, and controlled independently. Two internal stainless-steel tubes are placed inside the reactor to separate the catalytic bed from the pyrolysis zone. A quartz wool sheet and a metallic plate are placed over each tube and over the catalyst particles to avoid possible mixing between the char particles and the catalyst bed.

Fig. S2. XRD pattern of n-ZSM-5 zeolite.

Fig. S3. TEM images acquired over n-ZSM-5 zeolite.

Fig. S4. NH₃-TPD profile of n-ZSM-5 zeolite.

Fig. S5. Semiquantitative composition of pyrolysis vapours of isosorbide (99 wt.% from ALFA AESAR) in presence of n-ZSM-5 at 450 °C obtained using Pyr/GC-MS.

TABLES

Table S1. Physico-chemical properties of n-ZSM-5 zeolite.

Catalyst	[Si/Al] _{mol} ^a	S _{BET} ^b (m ² /g)	S _{MIC} ^c (m ² /g)	S _{MS+EXT} ^c (m ² /g)	V _T ^d (cm ³ /g)	Acidity ^e (mmol/g)
n-ZSM-5	42	445	316	127	0.512	0.28

^a Determined by ICP-OES.

^b BET surface area.

^c Micropore surface area (S_{MIC}) and External surface area (S_{EXT}), calculated from t-plot.

^d Total pore volume at P/P₀ ≈ 0.98.

^e Measured by TPD-NH₃.

Table S2. Ash content and elemental composition of the bio-char produced in thermal (TP) and catalytic pyrolysis (CP) of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning (GP) mixtures

Experiment	Ash content (wt.% _{char})	Elemental composition (wt.% _{char} ·daf)				
		C	H	N	S	O
TP 100GP	11.3	81.7	3.5	1.8	0.0	13.0
TP 80GP/20FW	12.1	81.2	3.4	1.5	0.0	13.9
TP 60GP/40FW	13.1	80.8	3.3	1.7	0.0	14.2
TP 100FW	15.3	78.1	3.4	1.9	0.0	16.6
CP 100GP	11.5	86.7	3.4	1.6	0.0	8.4
CP 80GP/20FW	12.7	84.9	3.7	2.4	0.0	8.9
CP 60GP/40FW	13.5	80.9	3.1	1.5	0.0	15.1
CP 100FW	16.1	84.9	3.4	2.0	0.0	9.8

daf: dry and ashes-free basis

Table S3. Elemental composition of the coke produced in catalytic pyrolysis (CP) of fruit wastes (FW) and garden pruning (GP) mixtures.

Experiment	Elemental composition (wt.% _{coke} ·daf)				
	C	H	N	S	O
CP 100GP	76.3	6.4	5.0	0.0	12.4
CP 80GP/20FW	74.0	5.7	8.2	0.0	12.1
CP 60GP/40FW	76.4	6.0	6.6	0.0	11.0
CP 100FW	77.1	6.8	5.5	0.0	10.6

daf: dry and ashes-free basis